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“A DOLLS REPLY TO ITS RIGHTFUL OWNER”

One afternoon, I was awakened by the noise,
Children chattered, boasting their new toys.
I, inside the box, abandoned with no choice,
Until I heard a pleasant and heavenly voice.

But what am I? A doll? A toy from neglecting hands.
Craft in a hurry with less quality,
Wearing a white shirt, blue shorts, a bit dirty,
Having a value of a hundred, no I think fifty.

Let me return to the voice so sweet,
I can't see her face because my eyes are still blurred,
She picks me up gently without uttering a word,
My heart skips like it is being stirred.

I am her shadow whenever she wanders.
When she is a rage, she punches me harder.
"I brace myself—will she set me on fire?
But no, she only hugs me tighter."

I realize that being with her, my value gets up.
Becoming a noble, from being a scrap,
She bought me clothes and sewed me a new life,
Unlike with the other dolls, she puts me on top.

One time, a Bob Marley's tune begins to play,
"Is this love, is this love, is this love that I'm feeling"
The world stops, and I start contemplating and validating,
Is it possible that a doll would fall in love? That is what I'm asking.

Then I realized that it is impossible to happen,
I am just a doll; however, she is a human.
We both live in the same place with different dimensions,
She can have another human partner, not to mention.

A spark, a wish, a whispered spell,
Did fate unravel? I cannot tell.
“From stitches to skin, from thread to heart”
A voice, a heart—what have I become?
“At last, I wonder—am I made for love?
With heart now beating, is fate not enough?”

Here we are, falling in love with each other
between what *is* and what *should never be*.
From stitches to skin, from thread to heart,
I would choose to remain hers—forever.